

AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG GRADUATE LEVEL STUDENTS UNDER THE NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020

Keerti Gupta

*Research scholar, Department of B.Ed./M.Ed., M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly (UP)
India*

Prof. Sudhir Kumar Verma

Department of B.Ed./M.Ed., M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly (UP) India

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Abstract

The modern era is the era of science. In which Digital India campaign is playing an important role in transforming the entire country into a strong society. A new education system in line with the ambitious goals of 21st century education will develop the necessary knowledge, values, attitudes, skills and abilities such as logical thinking, creativity, scientific thinking, ability to communicate and cooperate, multilingualism, problem solving, ethical thinking in the year 2020. And holistic development of Karma, social responsibility and concern and digital literacy etc. have been promoted, in which Artificial Intelligence plays an important role. Keeping in view the requirements of the twenty-first century, Artificial Intelligence provides a suitable environment to develop all-round talent and creative personality in the students keeping in mind the objectives of education. Through the presented research paper, students imagine the importance and awareness of artificial intelligence in the modern world and society in the field of technology, which is a powerful medium to shape the future world.

Key - National Education Policy 2020, Artificial Intelligence

Introduction:

Education is a discipline that elevates humans from animality to humanity. It acquaints individuals with society and helps them establish themselves within it. Through education, a person studies various aspects of society and strives to lead a successful life. (Patel, Surender & Verma, S K. (2024)). Teachers have an important role to play in teaching as well as an

integral component of our continuum of schooling. It is up to the teachers to establish critical fundamental skills, communication, attitudes, importance judgment and the correct adoption of our students (Kumar, Pradeep & Verma, S K. (2024)). India of the 21st century is the India of Digital India campaign, which on one hand is promoting a digitally empowered society and knowledge based economy and on the other hand, recognizing the bidirectional relationship between education and technology, it is also promoting technology integrated teaching-learning. The current Education Policy 2020 emphasizes on more practical and applied aspects in the fast pace of technological development. Technology has helped educational institutions in making teaching-learning quality, interesting, simple and effective. Education is a discipline that elevates humans from animosity to humanity. It acquaints individuals with society and helps them establish themselves within it. Through education, a person studies various aspects of society and strives to lead a successful life.³ Artificial intelligence exists when a machine can have human-based skills such as learning, reasoning, and solving problems. The current Education Policy 2020 focuses on the development of current technology areas such as Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Blog Chain, Smart-board, Adaptive Computer Testing etc. regarding the use and integration of technology. Technology is rapidly influencing many aspects of human society, including education, on a large scale; this can be directly used in the field of education. At its core, artificial intelligence reduces the cost of predictive tasks by using available data to fill in information gaps. Use of Artificial Intelligence. The application of artificial intelligence can be in such a way that the need for conscious deliberation required to understand the impact of a particular technology can be presented in a very effective way by artificial intelligence. Along with this, NRF's three-pronged approach can also be adopted in the context of research into impactful technologies - such as advancing core artificial intelligence research, development and application of application-based research, health, agriculture and climate crisis. Like using artificial intelligence to face global crises and establishing international research. Data is an important fuel for artificial intelligence based technologies, for which it is important to increase awareness of laws and standards related to privacy issues, data-retention, data-security etc. Along with this, it is also very important to raise and discuss educational, ethical and social issues related to the development and use of artificial intelligence based technology. Computer science has immense importance in the field of

education. One branch of which is Artificial Intelligence. Through which we can significantly improve and progress the level of education. Through this, not only is there a change in the way teachers work, but there is also a revolution in the way students learn. With the rise of Artificial Intelligence in education, it is being used in many different ways to help students learn. Task Automation by Artificial Intelligence in Education, Personalized Learning, Virtual Reality, Universal Access, Smart Content Creation, Learning Management System, Teacher Training, Robotics, Identifying Classroom Weaknesses, AI Powered Chat-bots, Universal Access, Instant Feedback, Smart Content, Computer Games, Natural Language Processing, Intelligent Systems, Vision Systems, Speech Recognition are being used at a rapid pace by teachers and students at various levels of education. Due to which they will develop skills and gain expertise in doing any work. Which he will be able to use for the progressive development of himself and the society . Artificial intelligence shapes our future more powerfully than the inventions of any other century. The possibilities hidden in artificial intelligence technology have far greater positive impacts than the challenges they pose. The impact of artificial intelligence is fueling another generation of automation and is becoming a strong factor in implementing routine tasks performed by less skilled people on smart-phones and tablets. It is present in our lives and education systems today. With its help, life of both students and teachers can be made easier. Artificial Intelligence gives every student the opportunity to get quality education and makes the learning process personalized. Therefore, we can say that artificial intelligence will be of great help to our future and present generations. If it is used properly then it will prove to be a major boon for human life and will make human life simple and Study of related literature.

Related Literature

Kumar, A. (2017). Conducted a study on artificial intelligence and future prospects, the main points of which were the challenge to employment, intelligence in jobs through skills, threat to privacy, which concluded that artificial intelligence is a threat to prosperity and development as well as regulation on its use.

Truck, A. and Virkel, H. and A. Hartmann (2020). In their study on the current state of combining human and artificial intelligence for strategic organizational decision making, they found that artificial intelligence provides a platform of combined possibilities.

Dong, Y. and Hod, Song (2020). How human intelligence, consciousness, and cognitive computing influence the development of artificial intelligence. In its research work, it has been found that the form of “co-evolution” can be realized between humans and AI machines and the use of AI is continuously increasing in areas like education, commerce and medical treatment.

Tai, C.M. (2020). In a study on “The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Human Society and Bioethics,” it found that it highlights both the positive and negative sides of what the country knows as the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Along with this, AI should also include bioethics like beneficence, value assessment, clarity, accountability etc. because without the capacity of authentic human emotions and empathy, AI will remain a machine.

Arya, M.L. (2021). In his study, he concluded that with the use of artificial intelligence, the lives of both teachers and students can be made simple and useful.

Yang, J.S. and Ogata, and Matsui, and Chen (2021). In his study Human-centered Artificial Intelligence in Education: Seeing the Invisible through the Visual, AI is being used to evaluate new designs, methods and tools and to inform research, education, policy and practice. Kams, M. (2021). conducted its own study on the long-term impact of artificial intelligence and robotics on higher education, concluding that the potential of AI and robots has attracted widespread interest among the public, government, and academia.

Ahmed, F.S. (2023). Human impairment in decision making, conducted a study on laziness in education and the impact of artificial intelligence on security, the conclusion of which was that it was found that AI is hindering human's decision making ability and making him lazy, which has an impact on his security. And it is also affecting privacy.

Kesari, S. (2023). has influenced both the positive and negative aspects of artificial intelligence, in which humans must consider both the advantages and disadvantages of innovation research and development.

Seth, Deepika. (2023). He did his study on the role of Artificial Intelligence in education, in which it was found that along with the merits, there are also some demerits in Artificial Intelligence, about which we should be aware and use it.

Sajid, H. (2023). In his article on “AI Consciousness: Exploring Possibilities, Theoretical Frameworks and Challenges”, AI is a complex and fascinating concept that has attracted and

influenced the interest of researchers, scientists, philosophers and the public. Awareness as well as risk in AI systems should be studied in detail.

Jarrahi, H.M., Smith, P. and Askew, D. and Eshradhi, A. (2023). In its study on Artificial Intelligence and Knowledge Management: A Partnership between Humans and AI, it concluded that AI is enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of humans through the creation, grammar and retrieval, sharing and application of knowledge.

Patel, Surendra & Verma, S K. (2023). Increasing Trend of Technology Usage among Secondary School Teachers in accordance with the National Education Policy 2020. The objective of this research is to understand the growing interest among teachers in using technology for teaching following the COVID-19 pandemic and the National Education Policy 2020. The study aims to explore how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can be utilized to make the teaching-learning process more engaging and effective. A descriptive research method was employed, with a survey method selected for data collection. A self-constructed questionnaire was used to gather data, and hypothesis testing was conducted using mean, standard deviation, and T-test. The findings of the research indicate that the use of ICT by teachers in teaching has a positive impact on the academic achievement of secondary-level students.

Kumar, Narendra & Verma, S K. (2023). A Study of the Impact of Family Environment on the Study Habits of Students in Upper Primary Schools Based on Government and Non-Government School. The family environment and study habits play a crucial role in a student's education and development. Both of these areas can contribute significantly to a student's progress, leading to their social, economic, and mental advancement. Support and encouragement within the family environment increase a child's self-support, which can lead to greater success in their studies. Learning ideal time management within the family setting can help children achieve excellence in their studies. The atmosphere of respect and thoughtfulness in the family can inspire children to study in new and thoughtful directions. Encouragement of a healthy lifestyle in the family can make children more responsible in their studies.

Kumar, Rakesh. (2024). In our article on Environment of Artificial Intelligence in Education: Prospects of Artificial Intelligence in B.Ed., we found that the prospects of Artificial Intelligence in B.Ed. are quite exciting and it has many potential uses.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence is believed to have started in India in the recent years. Artificial Intelligence means intelligence created by humans. Man created a machine that could work like him and help him in his work. The main difference between humans and artificial intelligence (robots) is that humans work with their own discretion and robots work according to humans. Artificial intelligence is a computer-controlled robot that works with the help of specially designed software. It uses machine learning. Today, courses related to applied artificial intelligence as well as robotics and automation engineering etc. are being started in universities. Today, artificial intelligence is trying to bring significant changes in the traditional methods of education. Whether we talk about teaching methods in education today or the universal development of students and institutions, new dimensions of learning are being created by using Artificial Intelligence. Man invents new machines as per his need and in the same direction, to make his work easier, simpler and easier, he has created a computer-controlled robot. It has the ability to think, understand and work like a human being. Today, most of the countries in the whole world are experimenting on it. In India, the use of artificial intelligence is still in its infancy. Studies are being done on it in different areas of the country. Strategic plans are being prepared on this in India. The National Education Policy 2020 especially emphasizes on the development of digital education along with the study and use of Artificial Intelligence in the teaching process. The coming time will be of Artificial Intelligence i.e. machines, which will provide intensity and efficiency in human work. For this, it is necessary that the government should also make policies and rules regarding human interest, keeping in mind its advantages and disadvantages.

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